

PLLA honeycombs activated by plasma and high energy excimer laser for stem cell support

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Abstract

We have focused our research on the construction and activation of honeycomb structure on perfluorinated substrate which was treated by a following KrF laser treatment (wavelength 248 nm). As the honeycomb material we have selected biopolymer poly-L-lactic acid, which has been soluted in the mixture of chloroform/methanol. By improved phase separation during dip coating procedure the micropattern of plasma treated FEP substrate was prepared. PLLA micropattern was subsequently treated with an excimer laser with laser fluence 10 mJ.cm^{-2} and with different number of laser pulses. Alternatively, as a secondary treatment we have used plasma exposure. Surface morphology of the pristine and laser treated PLLA pattern was studied by both atomic force and scanning electron microscopy. Surface chemistry was analyzed by energy dispersive spectroscopy and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. Cell metabolic activity of adipose stem cells was evaluated with MTS test, cell numbers on selected samples were also determined. Morphology of cells growing on the honeycomb-like pattern was studied in detail by fluorescence microscopy. We have been able to determine such combination of honeycomb pattern laser treatment and plasma treatment that led to construction of an excellent scaffold for adipose stem cell culture.

Keywords: honeycomb pattern; organic coating; laser treatment; biopolymer; morphology; cytocompatibility

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1. Introduction

The development of micro and nano-patternes of various materials can be traced to 1911 regarding the effect of topology and fibrous scaffolds on frog embryo [1]. More recent example is the study of the colours found in particular butterflies' wings which can be artificially reproduced by using polystyrene when several grating may be prepared [2], such structures may find use as photonic materials [3]. The important followed procedure is the biomimicry technique, which applies the pattern design by mimicking a specific part of organism [4]. Biomimicking approaches were used in medical industry due to their possibility to simulate the desired surface design by application of surface patterning techniques. Thus, polygon shapes and nano-pillar shapes of various dimensions and spacing may be applied e.g. for orthopedic implants due to their antibacterial properties [5], some of the constructed materials may be also used for in vivo experiments, where the adhesion of epithelial cells is affected by different properties of nano-porous surfaces [6]. The particular choice of material is based on the targeted application, the in vitro or in vivo study and more importantly the type of studied cell line. The main advantage of application of polymer materials [7-9] is the possibility to modify their surface properties easily, thus changing both their morphology or surface chemistry [10-12]. The applied procedures may be based on plasma modification, wet techniques based on grafting procedures or excimer laser exposure, where also the different patterns typically linear, dot or more complex pattern may be prepared [13-17].

A variety of methods are utilized to create surface patterns of different sizes and shapes. These methods can be categorized into two main groups: top-down and bottom-up approaches [18]. They may also be integrated with additional techniques or replaced by unconventional patterning methods [19,20]. The top-down approach typically involves removing molecules or atoms from a material through the use of light beams [21-23], exposure to particles, or ions [24]. In contrast, the bottom-up approach involves assembling complex structures from molecular or atomic blocks or stacks through assembly processes [25]. While the top-down method is often more suitable for creating precise patterns on large surfaces, the bottom-up approach tends to yield patterns with fewer defects. Several lithographic techniques are used for patterning solid state substrates, including photolithography [26]. This process involves using UV light to chemically modify and then remove either the exposed or unexposed regions of photoresist through chemical etching. Photomasks are frequently modified using digital mirrors [27] or by creating reusable polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) photomasks [28].

Electron beam lithography (EBL) enables the preparation of high-resolution patterns on a polymer-based resist by using focused electron beams, which alter the resist's solubility and

facilitate the selective removal of exposed (positive tone) or non-exposed (negative tone) areas through etching [29,30]. Soft lithography [31,32] encompasses a set of patterning techniques that use soft molds to replicate periodic surface patterns down to approximately 10 nm, applicable to flexible surfaces and capable of creating patterns over large areas [33]. Key techniques derived from soft lithography include nanoimprint lithography (NIL), which transfers patterns from a master mold to a polymeric resist through mechanical deformation [34-36], and microcontact printing (μ CP), a method that generates surface structures with lateral dimensions ranging from micrometers to nanometers by pressing polymeric surfaces against master stamps [37]. Patterns produced by UVNIL are highly stable under various conditions and can be applied in fields such as biofilm production and cytocompatibility [38-40].

Not only „classic“ polymers, but also biopolymers can be patterned into various structures each of them exhibiting specific properties that can be used in several of biological applications [7,8,9, 41, 42], and which can be also significantly altered by plasma or laser exposure. Biopolymers such as chitosan, starch or PLLA due to laser irradiation may alter their morphology or porosity [43,44], which enables their employment in cell growth procedures. Moreover, specific honeycomb structures may be constructed by improved phase separation techniques, such as PLLA, PS or cellulose acetate [44-48]. These patterns may be used as further templates for lithography technique or directly applied as a substrate for cytocompatibility or antibacterial properties. Biomedical applications of micro-nanopatterned structures are based on the applicability of micro/ nanopatterned structures specifically the patterns which have been formed on the basis of biocompatible or bio functional polymer materials with wide possibility of their studies related to the biomedical field [49-54]. Due to their interesting properties and the constant advancements made in their design and fabrication, micro and nano patterned structures have gained importance both in material and tissue engineering.

We have constructed honeycomb scaffolds by the process of improved phase separation technique on plasma activated per fluorinated substrate, which was subsequently used to study the cytocompatibility of stem cells on such surfaces. The advantage of this approach is based on the synergy based on the subsequent activation of honeycomb pattern with an excimer laser or argon plasma, with significant changes in both surface morphology and also surface chemistry. We have described the cytocompatibility and cell interaction with these honeycomb altered units with stem cells which expanded the possibilities of these methods in the field of vascular substitutes, where ASC stem cells isolated from adipose tissue have the function of

pericytes, which support vascularization, i.e. the creation of the preparation of vascularized vascular substitutes for vascular supply.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials and polymer modification

As primary substrate for subsequent plasma treatment, we used perfluorethylenepropylene (FEP) polymer (the density of $2.15 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, $50 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ thick foils) supplied by Goodfellow Ltd., Great Britain. Plasma treatment was performed by diode Ar plasma discharge with Balzers SCD 050 device. The gas purity used was 99.997 % with the gas pressure of 10 Pa. Subsequent parameters of plasma discharge was plasma power of 8 W, electrode distance set up to 50 mm. The surface activation with plasma was accomplished at room temperature (RT) exposure time was 240 s.

For HCP construction, we used poly-L-lactic acid which was obtained from Goodfellow as oriented PLLA foils of $50 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ thickness (density $1.05 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, $T_g \sim 60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). PLLA solutions were homogenized in ultrasonic bath XUBA 1 (Grant, UK) for 300 s. PLLA microstructures on the FEP were created by the dip-coating method, a biopolymer solution on the basis of chloroform and methanol (2 g PLLA in 100 ml, in ratio 85:15) was prepared, mixed with PLLA until a homogeneous solution was prepared.

2.2 Analytical methods

Surface morphology

The study of material surface morphology was performed using atomic force microscope Dimension ICON (Bruker Corp.). ScanAsyst[®] mode in air was applied with a silicon tip on Nitride Lever SCANASYST-AIR and spring constant of $0.4 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$. Acquired data were processed by the NanoScope Analysis software.

To monitor the material surface morphology, we used the scanning electron microscope LYRA3 GMU (Tescan, Czech Republic). The acceleration voltage was set up to 10 kV. Sample metallization was conducted by a sputtering technique (Quorum Q300T equipment) using a Pt conductive layer with thickness of 10 nm (Pt target, purity 99.9995 %).

Wettability and zeta potential

Surface wettability of the studied material was determined by advancing water contact angle measurement using goniometry. The CA analysis was done at RT with distilled water on

a six different positions of 3 samples using the Surface Energy Evaluation System (Advex Instruments, Czech Republic) with automatic pipetting and drop volume of $8.0 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{l}$. The method error is of $\pm 5 \%$.

Electrokinetic analysis, more specifically, zeta potential determination of the tested films was carried out using the SurPASS Instrument (Anton Paar GmbH, Austria) by two methods (streaming current and streaming potential) and calculated using two equations (Helmholtz-Smoluchowski, HS, and Fairbrother-Mastins, FM). A comparison of both methods can help to evaluate surface roughness and morphology of the films because the HS equation is strongly affected by the sample geometry. The samples were studied inside an adjustable gap cell with $0.001 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ KCl as an electrolyte at constant pH=6.7 at room temperature.

Surface chemistry

The elemental composition on the sample surface was analyzed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) using spectrometer ESCAProbeP (An Omicron Nanotechnology). The source was monochromatic X-ray at energy of 1486.7 eV. Atomic concentrations of elements were determined from the individual peak areas using CasaXPS software. Another method for detection of elemental concentration was energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) using an F-MaxN analyzer and SDD detector (Oxford Instruments, UK). The applied acceleration voltage for EDS was 10 kV. The substrates were covered with the Pt conductive layer of 10 nm thickness by a diode sputtering method (Quorum Q300T).

2.3 Cytocompatibility

Cell cultivation on the samples

Prior to the cell seeding, the tested materials were inserted into wells of 24-well polystyrene plates (TPP, Trasadingen, Switzerland, inner well diameter 1.5 cm) and sterilized by UV. Adipose stem cells (ASCs) were seeded on the materials in a seeding density of $25\,000 \text{ cells}/\text{cm}^2$ ($50\,000 \text{ cells}/\text{sample}$) and cultured for 3 days in DMEM cultivation medium (Sigma-Aldrich, MO, USA), supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS; Sebak GmbH, Aidenbach, Germany) and gentamicin ($40 \mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, LEK, Ljubljana, Slovenia) at 37°C in an air atmosphere with 5% CO_2 . Three independent samples of each scaffold type as tested.

Evaluation of the cell number

On days 1, 2, 3 and 7 after cell seeding, the cells on the samples were rinsed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde for 15 min. The cell nuclei were visualized by a method of fluorescence DNA staining using DAPI (Sigma Aldrich) for 1 hour and photographed by an Olympus IX71 epifluorescence microscope (objective 10 x), equipped with a DP 70 digital camera (both from Olympus, Japan), each sample in 10 visual fields. The cell number was counted from microphotographs automatically the Fiji ImageJ software.

Cell morphology

The cell morphology and spreading was evaluated by the filamentous actin (F-actin), visualized by staining cells with phalloidin conjugated with tetra-methylrhodamine (TRITC) (Sigma-Aldrich, MO, U.S.A., Cat. No. P1951), in order to evaluate the assembly of actin cytoskeleton and the shape and spreading of cells on the tested materials. The samples were stained for 1 hour at room temperature, and photographed by Olympus IX 51, DP 70 digital camera, (objective 20 x) in 5 representative fields for each of 3 independent samples for each experimental group.

Cell metabolic activity

The cells growth and cell surviving on the tested samples was further estimated by cell metabolic activity, which is regarded as an indirect marker of the number and proliferation activity of cells. This activity was estimated spectrophotometrically on days 1, 2, 3 and 7 after cell seeding, using a MTS Cell Proliferation Assay Kit (Colorimetric), Cat. No. ab197010 (Abcam, Cambridge, UK). The principle of the assay is the reduction of the yellow MTS tetrazolium compound by NAD(P)H-dependent dehydrogenase enzymes, present in living and metabolically active mammalian cells, and generation of a purple formazan, which is quantified by measuring the absorbance at 490 nm. Before the procedure, the samples with cells were moved to fresh cell culture well plates in order to exclude the influence of cells adhering and growing on the well bottoms under and around the tested samples. The MTS assay was then performed according to the manufacturer's protocol. Briefly, the cells were incubated with the MTS reagent and incubated for 1 hour (37° C, 5% CO₂). The resulting solution was then moved into 96-well polystyrene test plates (Sigma-Aldrich, 200 µm of the solution per well). Absorbance was measured using the VersaMax ELISA microplate reader (Molecular Devices

LLC, Sunnyvale, CA, USA) at the wavelength of 490 nm. One sample without cells for each experimental group and time point was used as a control to set the background for the measured absorbance. Polystyrene wells in a 24-well plate were used as a reference material.

Figure 1 Scheme of the process of honeycomb pattern formation followed by laser treatment with an excimer laser.

3. Result and discussion

3.1 Preparation of honeycomb PLLA pattern and substrate properties

In this work, we have followed the same procedure described in [45], we have used FEP polymer as a primary substrate. The pristine polymer itself, if it is used for the procedure of improved phase separation from the mixture solution of chloroform and methanol, does not lead to sufficiently homogeneous layer. The plasma pre-processing is an essential step to improve the surface properties in a manner that its surface free energy is increased thus the wettability is increased and surface contact angle is decreasing. From our previously conducted and published experiment we came to conclusion that the optimal argon plasma power is 8 W, while the most homogeneous pattern is usually created for longer exposure times for most of studied polymers in our group. Therefore exposure time 240 s as the only one exposure time have been used. The scheme of the applied procedure is summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 2 Surface morphology of pristine and plasma treated FEP (8 W/240 s). At the bottom left the surface chemistry from EDS analysis and at the bottom right the contact angle of plasma treated and pristine FEP is introduced.

As it is obvious from Figure 2, plasma exposure of FEP polymer significantly altered both his surface morphology and surface chemistry. The worm-like structure at nanometer scale is induced on FEP by plasma exposure, the more pronounced effect is observed for higher plasma power and plasma exposure time. The plasma power 8 W and exposure time 240 s increases the FEP roughness up to 8.2 nm. The morphology changes are complemented with the changes of surface chemistry, as it is obvious from the EDS results, also introduced in Figure 2. The pristine FEP surface has only carbon and fluorine on its surface, while the plasma pretreatment increases induced the oxygen containing groups on its surface up to 14.5 at. %. Also a small amount of nitrogen is induced on the surface, the increase of both oxygen and

nitrogen containing groups are complemented with the decrease of fluorine (the fluorine atoms are replaced by oxygen in the upper modified layers). The changes of both surface morphology and chemical composition induces a sharp decrease of surface wettability (Figure 2 bottom right), the hydrophobic FEP surface becomes hydrophilic with the fall of contact angle to 34°. Such massive change in surface physico-chemical properties of FEP surface builds a strong basis for construction of honeycomb biopolymer films, as will be shown further in the paper.

3.2 Surface morphology - AFM

Such treated surface can be easily used for the construction of honeycomb pattern by the application of improved phase separation method, which was successfully applied e.g. for biopolymer PLLA [45] or polystyrene [47]. On the basis of already published results, we decided to prepare the honeycomb PLLA pattern, while the 2 g of PLLA in volume solution was used (by volume 85:15 – chloroform and methanol). Such honeycomb pattern is stable, and with optimal homogeneity of the pattern. In this research we decided to apply the same procedure of the plasma surface modification used for the exposure of primary substrate and to apply it as a „secondary“ surface modification of already formed surface honeycomb pattern, or, to use an excimer laser as an secondary treatment. Since a significant surface changes were observed with application of excimer laser on polystyrene honeycombs [47] we decided to study this modification procedure also for PLLA honeycomb. On the basis of the previously achieved results we have chosen the laser fluence 10 mJ.cm⁻² as the energy of the excimer beam with the variation of pulses from 100 to 6000.

The excimer laser treatment of already constructed honeycomb units of FEP substrate changes its surface morphology, as it is presented in Figure 3. The lower number of laser pulses leads to only minor changes of the honeycomb unit morphology. With larger number of laser pulses we can see partial disruption of the honeycomb unit, some „walls“ are disrupted, the pattern shape is still maintained, the process is complemented with slight increase of surface roughness (up to 292 nm). With substantial increase of laser pulses number up to 3000 we can see the disruption of pattern, even the main honeycomb shape is still preserved, which an important parameter for subsequent study of cytocompatibility.

Figure 3 Surface morphology of laser exposer PLLA honeycomb pattern on FEP. The samples exposed with laser fluence 10 mJ.cm^{-2} and number of laser pulses 100, 500 and 3000 were studied. R_a represents the average surface roughness, S represents and effective surface area.

3.3 Zeta-potential

By the synergistic effect of surface chemistry and morphology changes the dramatic modification of zeta-potential was observed, as it is documented in Figure 4. We can see that the formation of the honeycombs dramatically increase the zeta-potential of the surface compared to the pristine FEP (green line), and the surface becomes more hydrophilic. The result of the zeta potential values for both Helmolz-Smochulovski and Fairbrother-Mastins are not different, which implicates the there are no changes in charge of surface on the altered substrates. The increase of number of laser pulses (increase of laser dose) led to decrease of zeta-potential values, a steady decrease was observed up to number of laser pulses 6000 with the value of zeta potential even lower (higher in absolute value) compared to pristine PLLA honeycomb pattern on FEP. This changes may be based on two different phenomena. The first one is that oxygen containing groups on the surface of honeycomb PLLA pattern are disrupted, more specifically ablated from the surface, and/or the oxygen is driven to diffuse into to

polymer bulk. These phenomena were observed earlier for different polymers [7, 8, 10, 14]. But, on the basis of AFM images of treated honeycombs after higher number of laser pulses it is evident, that besides the alteration of honeycomb units there is also presence of ablation and/or PLLA melting of the biopolymer over all area, where in the “lower areas” of pattern the revelation of the substrate occurs. Even the FEP substrate is plasma treated, it is still able to decrease the structure’s wettability, due to presence of fluorine atoms. With such partial ablation of the biopolymer, which will be also confirmed in the next paragraph aimed on SEM analysis, the zeta-potential may even overcome the values of pristine foil.

Figure 4 Zeta-potential of pristine honeycombs of PLLA, and laser treated PLLA honeycombs with 10 mJ.cm^{-2} and number of laser pulses 500, 1000, 3000 and 6000. For evaluation, the methods of Helmholtz-Smochulowski (HM) and Faibrother-Mastins (FM) were used.

3.4 SEM ans EDS analysis

The surface morphology changes were also studied with scanning electron microscopy, the results are introduced in Figure 5. If we increase the number of laser pulses, no significant changes in the surface morphology of the honeycomb pattern are observed for lower number of pulses (1st line of Figure 5).

Figure 5 Scanning electron microscopy images of surface morphology of honeycomb-like PLLA pattern on FEP treated with an excimer laser with laser fluence $10 \text{ mJ}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and number of laser beam pulses 100, 500, 3000 and 6000. The scanning areas were $100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$ and in the right upper corners the detailed images $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$ are introduced.

The unit structure is preserved till the number of pulses 500. However, even for number of pulses 500 we can see some changes in the pattern morphology. The changes are strongly induced for number of pulses above 3000 (bottom line of the Figure 5). It is obvious that the major pattern diminishes, due to two major factors. The first factor is the laser induced ablation

[55], which was also previously determined for laser exposed biopolymers PLLA and PHB. However, as it is evident, in this case also a melting of PLLA material is induced, probably due to increase of the surface temperature above 60° C, which is the glass transition temperature of studied biopolymer. Application on number of laser pulses 6000 lead to even more pronounced distortion of the honeycomb units, which are forming almost continuous layer on the plasma treated FEP substrate.

Figure 6 EDS spectra of a honeycomb-like pattern formed from PLLA on plasma-treated FEP samples subsequently treated with KrF laser with laser fluence 10 mJ.cm⁻² and number of laser pulses 100, 1000, 3000 and 6000. The elemental compositions (in at.%) of prepared patterns are introduced below each spectrum.

The laser induces also significant changes in surface chemistry as it is visible in EDS spectra (see Figure 6), and also EDS mapping for honeycomb structure after 1000 pulses (see Figure 7). From Figure 7 we can conclude, that for the lower number of laser dose (up to number of laser pulses 1000) there is a mild increase of oxygen concentration, which is induced by the distortion of biopolymer bond by the excimer energy, the disconnected bonds with radicals tend to interact with the oxygen atmosphere, thus creating the oxygen containing groups. With application of higher number of laser pulses this effect is suppressed, the major effect is the reorientation of the polymeric chains due to exceeding of the glass transition temperature, or the ablation of the biopolymer layer, when the most modified layer is released from the surface due to ablation effect.

Figure 7 EDS maps (fluorine, carbon and oxygen) of a honeycomb-like pattern formed from PLLA on plasma-treated FEP samples subsequently treated with KrF laser with laser fluence $10 \text{ mJ}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and number of laser pulses 1000. SEM image of the pattern is also introduced.

But, as it seems both from the morphology images in Figure 6, and more importantly EDS mapping, the continuous PLLA layer become discontinuous, and the plasma treated FEP surface, which serves as the basic substrate, is revealed. This effect is the key factor for decrease of oxygen concentration for higher number of applied laser pulses, which is accompanied with the increase of fluorine atomic concentration from the FEP substrate. We have determined only 4.56 at. % on the honeycomb pattern treated with 6000 pulses.

3.5 XPS analysis

Figure 8 XPS spectra of a honeycomb-like pattern formed from PLLA on plasma-treated FEP samples subsequently treated with KrF laser with laser fluence $10 \text{ mJ}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, pristine honeycomb pattern (a) and the pattern treated with number of laser pulses 1000 (b), 3000 (c) and 6000 (d) are introduced. The elemental compositions (in at.%) of treated patterns are also introduced.

The surface chemistry was also determined with X-ray photoelectron chemistry, which is able to reveal information from the very top surface, up to only ten atomic layers, which is

approx. 1 nm. We have determined also the surface chemistry of pristine PLLA honeycomb pattern, without laser exposure. Even on such surface we have determined non-zero fluorine concentration, which reveals the fact, that the honeycomb pattern is not monotonously continuous of the FEP substrate, however the amount of fluorine is very small, therefore the amount of exposed substrate is also small. With increasing number of laser pulses it is evident that the fluorine concentration increases, however there is no trend, no straight correlation between the number of laser pulses and fluorine concentration. This surprising fact is based probably on two facts – first is that the information is taken from the very top surface, therefore even the honeycomb structure is disrupted, the fluorine concentration is not increased significantly, since a layer of PLLA with small thickness is still remaining on the exposed FEP substrate even for higher number of laser pulses (e.g. 6000). The second fact is that the FEP substrate, which is treated with plasma (8 W and 240 s) has also increased atomic oxygen concentration, even before the honeycomb are constructed.

3.6 Cytocompatibility

Figure 9 Fluorescence images of adipose stem cell 3 days post seeding on PLLA honeycomb matrices treated by excimer laser with fluence 10 mJ.cm^{-2} and number of laser pulses 500, 1000 and 3000. Nuclei stained with DAPI are in blue, F-actin labelled with phalloidin-Atto 488 is in green. Scale is introduced within each image.

The main aim of this paper is to study the cytocompatibility of laser exposed samples. Firstly we would like to present the detailed images of stem cells on laser exposed honeycomb pattern (see Figure 9). The morphology of stem cells reveals that the shape is optimal on all laser treated samples. We would like to remind, that only representative samples have been chosen, just to show the detailed morphology of the cells and their attachment to the laser treated samples. As the primary evaluation of the laser treated honeycombs cytocompatibility we have chosen MTS test.

Figure 10 Cell metabolic activity – MTS test, for pristine PLLA honeycomb-like pattern on FEP (0), and honeycombs treated with excimer laser with fluence 10 mJ.cm^{-2} and number of pulses 500 - 6000, or PLLA honeycomb treated with argon plasma (8 W and 240 s), also results for pristine PLLA foil (pristine) and tissue polystyrene (PS) are introduced. The results are shown day 1, day 2, day 3 and day 7 from seeding.

The MTT assay is a colorimetric assay for assessing cell metabolic activity, the MTS assay is often described as a 'one-step' MTT assay, which offers the convenience of adding the reagent straight to the cell culture without the intermittent steps required in the MTT assay. The result presented in Figure 10 revealed excellent cell viability for both pristine honeycomb pattern and laser treated pattern, even better results compared to tissue polystyrene standard was

determined. Optionally, we have studied also the honeycomb PLLA pattern subsequently treated with the same plasma power as we used for the treatment of FEP as the primary substrate (plasma power 8 W and exposure time 240 s). The cell viability of subsequently treated honeycomb substrate is compared to pristine honeycomb pattern after 7 days from seeding, and slightly lower compared to those laser treated.

Figure 11 Cell adhesion and proliferation determination – number of cells for pristine PLLA honeycomb-like pattern on FEP (0), and honeycombs treated with excimer laser with fluence $10 \text{ mJ}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and number of pulses 500-6000, or PLLA honeycomb treated with argon plasma (8 W and 240 s), also results for pristine PLLA foil (pristine) and tissue polystyrene (PS) are introduced. The results are shown day 1, day 2, day 3 and day 7 from seeding.

The cytocompatibility of laser treated honeycomb samples are introduced in Figure 11, as well as the results of the honeycomb pattern which was plasma treated under the conditions introduced in previous paragraph. The laser treatment and plasma treatment does not affect the cell adhesion and the first stages of cell proliferation significantly. If we look at the cell numbers till the 2nd day from seeding, no significant changes are observed. However, the 3rd days from seeding, the proliferation on pristine PLLA sample is lower compared to treated samples. Seven

days from seeding there are some significant differences in cytocompatibility for selected samples. The outstanding results have been determined for honeycomb pattern which has been subsequently studied with plasma, the cytocompatibility was higher compared to PLLA honeycombs, but more importantly to tissue polystyrene. The cell number determined on PLLA honeycombs treated with excimer laser with number of pulses 1000 was also better compared to tissue polystyrene.

4. Conclusions

In this work, PLLA honeycomb-type microstructures were prepared on the surface of plasma treated FEP, and were subsequently treated with an excimer laser of additive plasma exposure. The PLLA pattern formation was induced by improved phase separation with application of a dip-coating technique. It was found, that the additional excimer exposure with laser fluence 10 mJ.cm^{-2} does not affect the honeycomb shape significantly till the number of pulses 1000, with higher number of applied laser pulses due to ablation and more importantly surface local melting above PLLA glass transition temperature the structure partially collapses. Even for lower integral laser dose the surface chemistry as well as wettability of the honeycomb pattern is significantly affected. Cell metabolic activity of adipose stem cells were evaluated with MTS test. In combination with determination of cell numbers we have determined, that optimal parameters are 10 mJ.cm^{-2} with number of pulses 1000 or plasma treatment with 8 W and 240 s, where the results were even better compared to tissue polystyrene.

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